

5-SHO‘BA TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH

THE PROBLEM OF STYLE IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: Given article is describes the problem of style in modern linguistics and its specific characteristics. At the same time specific individual stylistic features of Orwell’s works are analyzed.

Key words: Style, modern, linguistics, problem, method, individual, G. Orwell.

“Style, the Latin name for an iron pen, has come to designate the art that handles, with ever fresh vitality and wary alacrity, the fluid elements of speech. By a figure, obvious enough, which yet might serve for an epitome of literary method, the most rigid and simplest of instruments has lent its name to the subtlest and most flexible of arts”. This description of Walter Reilly is four centuries old. Researchers investigate the problem of style, but not everyone dares to define what style in literature is. An interesting method to solving this dilemma is written in the article by Erik Anderson’s “Style, optional rules and contextual conditioning”[1-2]. He says: “Style can be defined as a difference, more precisely - differences between two or more texts, so it is certainly a relative concept. To assert that a certain style is characteristic of a text is tantamount to asserting that it differs in a certain way from other texts”.

For some creations complete definition is enough, and based on style-forming rules which are directly about the research topic. In the case, it is needed to limit the definition scope. This research is concerned with the journalistic style’s problem and individual authorial manifestation in the essays of Orwell. It should be kept in mind that “you cannot mix language and speech styles, on the one hand, and language styles and genres of literature, on the other.” Since "the fixation of language styles for certain literary genres is characteristic only for certain trends in literature", it’s better to talk about the speech style of journalism and its features.

After all, the style of works written in different genres by the same writer will have differences dictated by the so-called "laws of the genre". For example, the style of journalistic works of G. Orwell differs seriously from the language of his novels, and much less from the language of his letters. This partly confirms the idea of V. Vinogradov that "in individual use, the boundaries of styles can shift, and one style can be used in the function of another to achieve one or another goal". A sense of style is

necessary for all specialists working with the language, including translators, especially since “the problem of preserving the author's individuality in translation is one of the most difficult”[3-5]. In the book *Essays on the Stylistics of the English Language*, the researcher notes that when defining the concept of "style of speech", different concepts are also mixed:

1) the style of speech as a system of regular correspondences of means of expression, characterized by the purpose and features of communication in this particular area of human activity;

2) style of speech as a manifestation of an individual manner of linguistic expression;

3) the style of speech as a technique for using the means of language to more effectively identify the content of the utterance.

"The translator must reflect, in a different linguistic form, the individual features of the author's language, preserve - within the limits of feasible - what is commonly called the style of the writer. These features are often eluding the translator's attention[5-8]. Therefore, "it is much more difficult to find the differences in the styles of individual authors reflected in the translation" than in the originals. Numerous theoretical works on translation studies only partially help to solve this problem, since "the art of a translator, in its highest achievements, consists in merging with the will of the author". And this cannot be taught. However, the translator must "be broadly educated, know the subject well enough, and refrain from working in an unfamiliar area". ("Translator's Charter"/Nelyubin L.L., 2001: 207). In the context of transferring the individual features of the original, this idea sounds like this: "A translator should not take on translations of those authors who, by their temperament and by the nature of their talent, are alien or hostile to him". Opinion of Chukovsky deserves special attention, since many of the translations made by this remarkable connoisseur of English and Russian almost a hundred years ago are still unsurpassed. Chukovsky was distinguished by an unusually careful attitude to the author's style: "The reflection of the writer's personality in the language of his works is called his individual style, inherent in him alone ... by distorting his style, we thereby distort his face - especially if, with the help of our translation, we impose him his own style, and in this way we will turn his self-portrait into a self-portrait of a translator"[9-10]. A special case of transferring the features of an individual author's language when translating an essay by G. Orwell is discussed in this work; before, in part, the distinctive features of the style of the famous publicist are analyzed. And in the next part of this chapter, we will focus on the history of the essay genre and its main features.

The problem of literary style still remains unresolved; in this issue there is a certain terminological non-differentiation. In our country, researchers distinguish between styles of language and styles of speech. Among the language styles, four are distinguished: colloquial, written, scientific and artistic. There are an infinite number of speech styles, their differences are primarily related to the purpose of the message and the personality (or group) of users. The separation of both linguistic and speech styles

is associated with the difference in their functioning. Newspaper-journalistic and individual authors are speech styles. Features of the journalistic style are determined by two main communicative attitudes: the attitude towards information and the attitude towards persuasion. The individual style of the writer, on the one hand, obeys the laws of the genre in which the author works, and on the other hand, reflects the inner world of the writer, his worldview. Differences between individual writing styles tend to be less noticeable in translation than in the original. In order to better preserve the linguistic features of a literary work in translation, it is necessary to have a good idea of the writer's work and carefully analyze his intentions. The temperament of the translator should match the character of the author as much as possible.

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